

Description of the Dataset

Desharnais

The dataset covers information from 81 distinct software projects, collected by Jean-Marc Desharnais from 10 organizations in Canada. These projects were carried out between 1983 and 1988. The dataset consists of 81 projects and 12 attributes, with size measured in function points.

Tabela 1: Description of the Desharnais Dataset

Attribute	Attribute Description	Data Type	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum Value	Maximum Value
Project	Project number.	Integer	-	-	1	81
TeamExp	Team experience in years.	Integer	2.185185185	1.415195314	-1	4
ManagerExp	Project managers' experience in years.	Integer	2.530864198	1.643824958	-1	7
YearEnd	Project completion year.	Double	85.74074074	1.222474721	82	88
Length	Project duration (in months).	Double	11.66666667	7.424621202	1	39
Effort	Effort measured in person-hours.	Integer	5046.308642	4418.767228	546	23940
Transactions	Number of processed transactions.	Integer	182.1234568	144.0350984	9	886
Entities	Number of entities.	Double	122.3333333	84.88212415	7	387
PointsNonAdjust	Unadjusted function points.	Double	304.4567901	180.2101585	73	1127
Adjustment	Adjustment factor.	Double	27.62962963	10.59179452	5	52
PointsAjust	Adjusted function points.	Double	289.2345679	185.7610879	62	1116
Language	Programming language.	String	1.555555556	0.707106781	1	3

Cocomo/Cocomo81

It was developed by Barry Boehm and encompasses a dataset with 63 software projects. It includes 17 complete numerical attributes, of which 15 are effort multipliers grouped into four distinct categories: product, platform, personnel, and project.

Tabela 2: Description of the Cocomo81 Dataset

Attribute	Attribute Description	Data Type	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum Value	Maximum Value
Rely	Required software reliability.	Double	1.036349206	0.193476693	0.75	1.4
Data	Database size.	Double	1.003968254	0.073430671	0.94	1.16
Cplx	Product complexity.	Double	1.091428571	0.20256307	0.7	1.65
Time	Execution time constraint.	Double	1.113809524	0.16163907	1	1.66
Stor	Main storage constraint.	Double	1.143809524	0.17942047	1	1.56
Virt	Virtual machine volatility.	Double	1.008412698	0.120592708	0.87	1.3
Turn	Required response time.	Double	0.971746032	0.080972709	0.87	1.15
Acap	Analyst capability.	Double	0.905238095	0.151507023	0.71	1.46
Aexp	Application experience.	Double	0.948571429	0.119243004	0.82	1.29
Pcap	Programmer capability.	Double	0.937460317	0.166510372	0.7	1.42
Vexp	Virtual machine experience.	Double	1.005238095	0.093375018	0.9	1.21
Lexp	Programming language experience.	Double	1.001428571	0.051988123	0.95	1.14
Modp	Use of modern programming practices.	Double	1.004126984	0.130935036	0.82	1.24
Tool	Use of software tools.	Double	1.016984127	0.085734679	0.83	1.24
Sced	Required development schedule.	Double	1.048388889	0.075586121	1	1.23
Loc	Lines of code.	Double	77.20984127	168.5093745	1.98	1150
Actual	Actual development effort in person-months.	Double	683.3206349	1821.582348	5.9	11400

Kemerer

The dataset represents data collected from an American IT and consulting company specializing in software development for data processing. The data collection took place in 1985. The oldest projects date back to 1981, while most began in 1983. These projects were classified as medium to large-scale, based on the number of thousands of source lines of code (measured in KSLOC). The dataset comprises 15 projects, each with 8 attributes.

Tabela 3: Description of the Kemerer Dataset

Attribute	Attribute Description	Data Type	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum Value	Maximum Value
ID	Project identifier.	Integer	-	-	1	15
Language	Programming language used in the project.	String	1.2	0.560611911	1	3
Hardware	Type of hardware used in the project.	String	2.333333333	1.67616342	1	6
Duration	Project duration in months.	Double	14.26666667	7.54478691	5	31
KSLOC	Estimated project size in lines of code.	Double	186.5733333	136.8174199	39	450
AdjFP	Adjusted function points.	Double	999.14	589.5920815	99.9	2306.8
RAWFP	Unadjusted function points.	Double	993.8666667	597.4261301	97	2284
EffortMM	Effort measured in person-months.	Double	219.2473333	263.0554285	23.2	1107.31

China

The dataset contains information on 499 Chinese software projects with resources from various companies. The China dataset comprises 19 attributes, with the measurement unit based on function points, and effort estimated in person-hours.

Tabela 4: Description of the China Dataset

Attribute	Attribute Description	Data Type	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum Value	Maximum Value
ID	Project identifier.	Integer	-	-	1	499
AFP	Adjusted function points of the project.	Integer	486.8577154	1059.171436	9	17518
Input	Number of inputs the system must process.	Integer	167.0981964	486.3385747	0	9404
Output	Number of outputs generated by the system.	Integer	113.6012024	221.2743742	0	2455
Enquiry	Number of queries or requests the system must handle.	Integer	61.6012024	105.4228399	0	952
File	Number of files used by the system.	Integer	91.23446894	210.2709839	0	2955
Interface	Number of interfaces with other systems.	Integer	24.23446894	85.0409961	0	1572
Added	Lines of code added.	Integer	360.3547094	829.842333	0	13580
Changed	Lines of code modified.	Integer	85.0621425	290.8570395	0	5193
Deleted	Lines of code deleted.	Integer	12.35270541	124.2241296	0	2657
PDR_AFP	Development ratio relative to adjusted function points.	Double	11.77054108	12.10564913	0.3	83.8
PDR_UFP	Development ratio relative to unadjusted function points.	Double	12.07975952	12.81871009	0.3	96.6
NPDR_AFP	Non-productive effort ratio adjusted to function points.	Double	13.26973948	14.00983971	0.4	101
NPDU_UFP	Non-productive effort ratio relative to unadjusted function points.	Double	13.62625251	14.84341606	0.4	108.3
Resource	Resources used during the project.	Integer	1.458917836	0.823729173	1	4
Dev.Type	Type of project development.	Integer	0	0	0	0
Duration	Project duration in months.	Double	8.719238477	7.347058438	1	84
N_effort	Normalized effort for comparison.	Integer	4277.641283	7071.248036	31	54620
Effort	Effort required for the project in person-hours.	Double	3921.048096	6480.8556	26	54620

Albrecht

It was published in 1983 by Albrecht and Gaffney. It consists of data from 24 software projects carried out in the 1970s at IBM Data Processing Services. The systems were developed using third-generation languages, such as COBOL and PL/1. The dataset contains two attributes: Functional Size (FP) and Development Effort (person-hours).

Tabela 5: Description of the Albrecht Dataset

Attribute	Attribute Description	Data Type	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum Value	Maximum Value
Size	The size of the software project, measured in thousands of lines of code (KLOC).	Double	21.875	28.4178947	0.5	105.2
Effort	The effort required to complete the project, measured in person-hours.	Double	647.625	487.9952612	199	1902

Nasa/Nasa93

Dataset compiled by NASA across five of its development centers. It includes information from 93 projects carried out between 1971 and 1987. The dataset consists of 17 attributes. The effort measurement unit is represented in person-months, and the project size is measured in KLOC (thousands of lines of code).

Tabela 6: Description of the Nasa93 Dataset

No.	Attribute	Attribute Description	Attribute Type	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
1	Rely	Required software reliability.	Categorical	1.11	0.13	0.88	1.40
2	Data	Application database size.	Categorical	1.00	0.07	0.94	1.16
3	Cplx	Product complexity.	Categorical	1.18	0.15	0.85	1.65
4	Time	Execution time performance constraints.	Categorical	1.13	0.20	1.00	1.66
5	Stor	Memory constraints.	Categorical	1.13	0.19	1.00	1.56
6	Virt	Volatility of the virtual machine environment.	Categorical	0.92	0.09	0.87	1.15
7	Turn	Required response time.	Categorical	0.96	0.09	0.87	1.15
8	Acap	Analyst capability.	Categorical	0.89	0.07	0.71	1.00
9	Aexp	Application experience.	Categorical	0.93	0.06	0.82	1.13
10	Pcap	Software engineer capability.	Categorical	0.91	0.10	0.70	1.00
11	Vexp	Experience with virtual machines.	Categorical	1.00	0.08	0.90	1.21
12	Lexp	Experience in programming languages.	Categorical	0.97	0.05	0.95	1.14
13	Modp	Application of software engineering methods.	Categorical	0.98	0.09	0.82	1.24
14	Tool	Use of software tools.	Categorical	1.00	0.09	0.83	1.24
15	Sced	Required development schedule.	Categorical	1.04	0.04	1.00	1.08
16	Loc	Lines of code.	Numerical	94.02	133.6	0.90	980.00
17	actual	Actual development effort in person-hours.	Numerical	624.41	1135.93	8.40	8211.00

Kitchenham

This dataset corresponds to data collected by the American technology company Computer Sciences Corporation (CSC). It contains information on 145 software development and maintenance projects carried out by CSC for various clients. The dataset includes 10 attributes, with project size measured in function points. Additionally, the attributes include the start date and the estimated completion dates of the projects, which took place between 1994 and 1999.

Tabela 7: Description of the Kitchenham Dataset

Attribute	Attribute Description	Data Type	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum Value	Maximum Value
Actual.duration	Actual duration of a project (in hours).	Double	206.4482759	134.0920046	37	946
Adjusted.function.points	Adjusted function points.	Double	527.6693103	1521.994936	15.36	18137.48
First.estimate	First effort estimate (person-hours).	Double	2855.972414	6789.287453	121	79870
Actual.effort	Actual project effort (person-hours).	Double	3113.117241	9598.008922	219	113930

SDR

Dataset collected from five software organizations in Turkey, following the COCOMO II format. It consists of 12 projects and contains 25 attributes, of which 22 are cost drivers. The project size was measured in estimated lines of code (LOC).

Nasa60

The Nasa60 dataset is a reduced version of Nasa93, containing information from 60 selected projects among the main ones carried out by NASA. These projects vary in terms of complexity and application domains, while maintaining the same 17 attributes that cover factors such as reliability, complexity, and estimated effort. The effort measurement unit

Tabela 8: Description of the SDR Dataset

Variable	Attribute Description	Data Type	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum Value	Maximum Value
ProjectID	Unique project identifier.	Integer	6.5	3.6056	1	12
PREC	Project precedence level.	Integer	2.25	2.0505	0	5
FLEX	Flexibility in process development.	Integer	2.6667	1.5570	0	4
RESL	Risk and uncertainty resolution.	Integer	2.0833	1.4434	0	4
TEAM	Teamwork capability.	Integer	2.9167	1.4434	0	5
PMAT	Maturity of project management processes.	Integer	1.5833	1.1645	0	3
RELY	Required software reliability.	Integer	1.5	0.9045	0	3
DATA	Application database size.	Integer	1.9167	1.1645	0	3
CPLX	Product complexity.	Integer	2.5	1.4460	0	4
RUSE	Required software component reuse.	Integer	1.9167	1.1645	0	3
DOCU	Required documentation for the project.	Integer	2.3333	1.3027	0	4
TIME	Execution time performance constraints.	Integer	1.0833	0.9962	0	2
STOR	Memory and storage constraints.	Integer	1.3333	0.8876	0	2
PVOL	Development platform volatility.	Integer	1.25	0.6216	0	2
ACAP	Analyst capability in the project.	Integer	1.0833	0.7930	0	2
PCAP	Capability of involved programmers.	Integer	0.6667	0.4924	0	1
PCON	Personnel continuity in the project.	Integer	0.4167	0.7930	0	2
AEXP	Analyst experience.	Integer	1.1667	0.8348	0	2
PEXP	Programmer experience.	Integer	0.9167	0.9003	0	2
LTEX	Experience in programming languages.	Integer	0.9167	0.6686	0	2
TOOL	Use of software tools.	Integer	1.9167	1.1645	0	3
SITE	Geographical diversity of the team.	Integer	2.3333	1.4355	0	5
SCED	Adjustments in the development schedule.	Integer	0.8333	0.8348	0	2
LOC	Application lines of code.	Integer	20920.0833	32158.3107	1369	114280
ACTUAL EFFORT	Actual effort measured in person-months.	Double	5.7333	6.8400	1	22

is represented in person-months, and the project size is measured in KLOC (thousands of lines of code).

Nasa18

The Nasa18 dataset is an even more reduced sample, consisting of 18 software projects selected from NASA’s general database. These projects were chosen to represent a diversity of domains and code sizes while maintaining the 17 attributes used in Nasa93. The effort measurement unit is represented in person-months, and the project size is measured in KLOC (thousands of lines of code).

ISBSG

The dataset from the International Software Benchmarking Standards Group (ISBSG) contains data on software development and enhancement projects collected over several years, with contributions from various industries worldwide.

Maxwell

The dataset was collected from a Finnish commercial bank and consists of 62 projects, each represented by 27 attributes. There are 22 categorical attributes believed to influence software productivity. The size attribute was measured in function points. The project start years ranged from 1985 to 1993.

Tabela 9: Description of the Maxwell Dataset

Attribute	Attribute Description	Data Type	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum Value	Maximum Value
Id	Initial project identifier.	Integer	-	-	1	62
Year	Project start year.	Integer	89.58064516	2.131330586	85	93
App	Name of the application under development.	String	2.35483871	0.993367747	1	5
Har	Hardware platform on which the application was created.	String	2.612903226	0.997617468	1	5
Db	Project information management system.	String	1.032258065	0.442338863	0	4
Ifc	Technology used for the user interface.	String	1.935483871	0.247675604	1	2
Source	Source code management system used.	Integer	1.870967742	0.337972303	1	2
Telomuse	Indicates whether IBM Telon is used for legacy applications.	Integer	0.241935484	0.431751442	0	1
Nlan	Number of programming languages used in the project.	Integer	2.548387097	1.019119185	1	4
T01	Customer involvement.	Integer	3.048387097	0.998809445	1	5
T02	Adequate development environment.	Integer	3.048387097	0.711208147	1	5
T03	Employee accessibility.	Integer	3.032258065	0.886469179	2	5
T04	Use of coding standards.	Integer	3.193548387	0.697506324	2	5
T05	Methods used.	Integer	3.048387097	0.711208147	1	5
T06	Tools used.	Integer	2.903225806	0.694467066	1	4
T07	Software logic.	Integer	3.241935484	0.899644445	2	5
T08	Specification volatility.	Integer	3.806451613	0.955376669	2	5
T09	Quality standards.	Integer	4.064516129	0.743738182	2	5
T10	Efficiency requirements.	Integer	3.612903226	0.893599072	2	5
T11	Installation prerequisites.	Integer	3.419354839	0.984276169	2	5
T12	Team analytical skills.	Integer	3.822580645	0.690074682	2	5
T13	Employee experience with the application.	Integer	3.064516129	0.955930029	1	5
T14	Teamwork skills.	Integer	3.258064516	1.007113777	1	5
T15	General teamwork skills.	Integer	3.338709677	0.745336284	1	5
Duration	Project duration in months.	Double	17.20967742	10.65115571	4	54
Size	Project size measured in lines of code.	Integer	673.3064516	784.0845051	48	3643
Time	Total time spent on the project in person-months.	Double	5.580645161	2.131330586	1	9
Effort	Total work in person-months for the project.	Double	8223.209677	10499.90317	583	63694

Tukutuku

Dataset containing information on various web application development projects, collected from multiple companies worldwide. This dataset includes 53 online projects and consists of nine numerical attributes describing each online application. Among these attributes are the number of media assets, the number of HTML or SHTML files used, and the development team's experience. The measurement unit used to quantify project size is based on function points, while development effort is estimated in person-hours.

Tabela 10: Description of the Tukutuku Dataset

Attribute	Attribute Description	Data Type	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Teamexp	Average number of years of experience of the web development team.	Ratio	3.8	2.0	1	10
Devteam	Number of people who worked on the software project.	Ratio	2.6	2.4	1	23
TotWP	Number of web pages in the application.	Ratio	69.5	185.7	1	2000
Textpages	Number of text pages in the application (one text page contains 600 words).					
TotImg	Number of images in the application.	Ratio	98.6	218.4	0	1820
Anim	Number of animations in the application.					
Audio/Video	Number of audio/video files in the application.					
Tot-high	Number of high-effort functionalities in the application.	Ratio	14.64	66.59	0	611
Tot-nhigh	Number of low-effort functionalities in the application.	Ratio	4.82	4.98	0	35

Miyazaki94

Dataset compiled by the Large Systems Users Group of Fujitsu. This data was collected from 48 COBOL systems developed across 20 different organizations, covering various departments within these organizations. Each project or system is described by nine attributes. The system size was measured by the number of COBOL source lines of code, expressed in thousands.

Tabela 11: Description of the Miyazaki94 Dataset

No.	Attribute	Attribute Description	Data Type	Feature Selection	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
1	ID	Project identifier.	Discrete	-	-	-	-	-
2	KSLOC	COBOL source lines of code in thousands, excluding comment lines.	Continuous	KLOC	70.792	87.5678	6.9	417.6
3	SCRN	Number of different input or output screens.	Discrete	SCRN	33.39	47.27	0	281
4	FORM	Number of different report forms.	Discrete	FORM	22.38	20.55	0	91
5	FILE	Number of different record formats.	Discrete	-	34.81	53.36	2	370
6	ESCRN	Total number of data elements across all screens.	Discrete	-	525.60	626.058	0	3000
7	EFORM	Total number of data elements across all forms.	Discrete	-	460.67	396.816	0	1566
8	EFILE	Total number of data elements across all files.	Discrete	-	1854.58	6398.605	57	45000
9	MM	Person-months required for the system.	Continuous	Man Month	87.475	228.7597	5.6	1586.0

Finnish

The dataset was collected by the TIEKE organization from nine companies in Finland. Initially, 40 projects were obtained, but due to missing values in some attributes of two projects, those data were excluded, resulting in 38 projects available for analysis. This dataset consists of 9 attributes, with project size measured in function points.

Tabela 12: Description of the Finnish Dataset

Attribute	Attribute Description	Data Type	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum Value	Maximum Value
ID	Project identifier.	Integer	-	-	1	38
dev.eff.hrs	Development effort (person-hours).	Double	7678.289474	7135.279948	460	26670
hw	Hardware used in the project.	Integer	1.263157895	0.644486409	1	3
at	Project duration.	Integer	2.236842105	1.496558404	1	5
FP	Function points.	Double	763.5789474	510.8337452	65	1814
co	Operational cost.	Double	6.263157895	2.728074368	2	10
prod	Productivity.	Double	10.07383974	7.086170078	1.472637	29.473262
lnsize	Project size in logarithm (log of project size).	Double	6.356578947	0.835490716	4.17	7.5
lneff	Logarithm of effort in hours (log of person-hours).	Double	8.396567158	1.179140322	6.131226	10.191295

NUSP05-FT

Dataset compiled by the University of Calgary from projects carried out by students in web applications and client/server systems. It includes information on 76 functionalities developed between 2005 and 2007. The dataset consists of 17 attributes, covering characteristics such as complexity, team experience, tools used, and actual effort measured in person-hours.

Tabela 13: Description of the NUSP05-FT Dataset

Attribute	Attribute Description	Data Type	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum Value	Maximum Value
ID	Unique project identifier	Integer	358.94	248.58	101	920
ObjType	Object type (PJ, FT, RQ)	Categorical	-	-	-	-
Effort	Actual effort in person-hours	Double	9.63	13.94	0.5	400
FunctPercent	Percentage of functionalities (% per category)	Numeric vector	-	-	-	-
IntComplex	Internal calculation complexity (1 to 5)	Integer	2.63	1.22	1.0	5.0
DataFile	Number of database files/tables	Integer	8.65	13.09	0.0	75.0
DataEn	Number of input items	Integer	42.24	63.11	0.0	314.0
DataOut	Number of output items	Integer	19.21	24.85	0.0	200.0
UFP	Unadjusted function point count	Integer	73.74	200.93	0.0	1714.0
Lang	Programming language used	Categorical	-	-	-	-
Tools	Development tools used	Categorical	-	-	-	-
ToolExpr	Experience with tools (in months)	Numeric	-	-	-	-
AppExpr	Level of experience with applications	Integer	2.65	1.14	1	5
TeamSize	Team size (minimum and maximum)	Numeric	-	-	-	-
DBMS	Database management system	Categorical	-	-	-	-
Method	Development methodology	Categorical	-	-	-	-
AppType	Application architecture type	Categorical	-	-	-	-